

MINEFIELD

by Mark Steere

Figure 1
Black wins

Figure 2
Prohibited glyphs

Figure 3
Black placements

INTRODUCTION

Minefield is a two-player game played on a square board of any size, initially empty. The top and bottom board edges are colored black. The left and right edges are colored white. Mark Steere designed Minefield in May 2024.

OBJECT OF THE GAME

Black must form an orthogonally (horizontally and/or vertically) interconnected path of black stones connecting the two black edges of the board. White must connect the two white edges. In **Figure 1**, Black has won.

PLAY

The two players, Black and White, take turns placing their own stones onto unoccupied points, one stone per turn, starting with Black. Passing is not allowed, but if you don't have an available placement, your turn is skipped.

Players are not allowed to form any of the glyphs (patterns) in **Figure 2** (or their reflections, rotations, or color reversals), explained in detail below. The blue dots are unoccupied points.

HARD CORNER

A “hard corner” is comprised of two stones of one color and one stone of the other color contained in a 2x2 area. The two same-colored stones are diagonally adjacent. One point within the area is unoccupied.

SWITCH

A “switch” is comprised of two stones of each color contained in a 2x3 or 2x4 area. Two stones of one color occupy diagonally opposite corner points. The two stones of the other color occupy the other two diagonally opposite corner points. The non-corner points are unoccupied.

EXAMPLE

In **Figure 3**, all of the **illegal placements** for Black are marked with **red dots**. They would all form hard corners, short switches, or long switches (see **Figure 2**). All of the other unoccupied points are legal placements for Black, including the two points marked with green dots.

DESIGN NOTES

Luis Bolaños Mures made a material contribution to Minefield. Minefield is an SPO OOSCG (Single Placement Only, Orthogonal Only Square Connection Game). Luis and I have advanced the state of the art in this tiny class, both independently and in collaboration.

AUTHOR'S NOTE

Feel free to publish this rule sheet and to program the game of Minefield. No licensing fee or royalties are expected. However, please don't change the name or the rules, and please attribute the game to me, Mark Steere. My other games can be found at marksteeregames.com.